

Infrared, Electron Microscopic and pH Dependence of Solubilities Studies of Solid Solutions of (Ca + Ba + Cd) Hydroxylapatites

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Infrared spectra of mixed calcium-barium-cadmium hydroxylapatites were studied in the 4000-200 cm^{-1} range and probable band assignments are given. The introduction of $\text{Ba}^{2+}/\text{Cd}^{2+}$ in calcium hydroxylapatite results in the formation of their solid solutions. In the infrared spectral studies of the samples, the vibrations corresponding to ν_4 of PO_4^{3-} ions and ν_1 and ν_2 of OH^{-1} are shifted to lower frequencies due to effect of binding energy and atomic mass as a result of substitution of Ca^{2+} by $\text{Ba}^{2+}/\text{Cd}^{2+}$. The crystal dimensions also increase and could be observed in the electron microscopic patterns of the samples. The solubilities of solid solutions of calcium-barium-cadmium hydroxylapatites determined in the pH range 5.0-8.0 decrease with increase in pH of the dissolving medium. This is due to dissolved phosphate ions functioning as proton acceptors. Being salts of weak acid the samples undergo hydrolysis in aqueous media. At a given pH the solubility of the samples increases with the increase of mole content of barium and cadmium in the mixed hydroxylapatites.

HYDROXYLAPATITE is assigned the formula $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2 \cdot (\text{CaHA})$. In recent years it has become the focus of attention that has been directed towards all the basic calcium phosphates for the elucidation of the process of calcification in general and for dentistry in particular. Hydroxylapatite is now recognised as the most important of the inorganic compounds in the structure of bones and teeth^{1,2}. Apatite undergoes a series of cationic and anionic exchange reactions³. $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Ba}^{2+}$ and/or Cd^{2+} replacement in CaHA is of extreme biological significance. They form the basis of incorporation of Ba^{2+} and Cd^{2+} into human skeletal system according to the reaction

This isomorphous replacement reaction in CaHA results in the formation of a series of solid solutions.

As a part of a series of physico-chemical investigations on the samples, the present work deals with the infrared, electronmicroscopic and pH dependence of solubilities studies of the samples.

Experimental

The details of preparation and identification of solid solutions of calcium-barium-cadmium hydroxylapatites were reported earlier^{4,5}. The samples used for infrared and electronmicroscopic studies

were acetone washed and air dried. All the compounds were identified and characterised by their X-ray powder diffraction patterns, taken with Siemens powder diffractometer with $\text{NaCl}(\text{TL})$ counter employing CuK_α (Ni filtered) radiation.

Spectroscopic techniques :

All bands were recorded on a grating Infrared spectrophotometer, Perkin Elmer Model 577, in KBr medium. A few mg of the sample was ground with 2 drops of nujol in an agate mortar. About 50 mg of a fine polyethylene powder (Vestolena 6016, Chem. Werke Nuels, Germany) was added. The resulting paste was melted at about 140° and pressed between glass plates to a slightly wedge-shaped film of average thickness 0.1 mm.

Electron microscopic analysis :

The scanning electron microscopic analysis on powder samples were examined using an Etec Autoscan Scanning Electron microscope with a 20 kV secondary electron mode using samples which were prepared from an alcohol dispersion on a polished carbon stub.

Solubility behaviour :

A knowledge of the solubility for hydroxylapatite is of extreme importance for undertaking the physiology of bone from the point of view of calcification and resorption. In addition, considerations of the occurrence of dental caries and the

TABLE 1—INFRARED ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF HYDROXYLAPATITES OF CALCIUM, BARIUM AND CADMIUM AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample	Molecular formula	G. atom ratio Ca+Ba+Cd P	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)		
			PO ₄ ³⁻ ν ₄	PO ₄ ³⁻ ν ₃	OH ⁻ ν _s
1.	Ca ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.665	570 sh	1075 br	3450 sh
2.	Ca _{9.1} Ba _{0.75} Cd _{1.15} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.667	565 sh	1072 br	3450 sh
3.	Ca ₈ Ba _{1.65} Cd _{0.35} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.664	560 sh	1070 br	3444 sh
4.	Ca _{4.15} Ba _{3.95} Cd _{1.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.662	560 sh	1065 br	3432 sh
5.	Ca _{2.15} Ba _{7.75} Cd _{0.1} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.665	555 sh	1065 br	3425 sh
6.	Ba _{4.6} Cd _{5.4} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.666	550 sh	1050 br	3375 sh
7.	Ba ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.664	542 sh	1048 br	3355 sh
8.	Cd ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.665	525 sh	1025 br	3300 sh

sh=sharp, br=broad.

Protective action of fluorine are based on the information about the solubility of hydroxylapatite. Such solubility studies have additional utility in soil chemistry in accounting for the action of phosphate containing fertilizers. The solubility studies were based exclusively on micro-determination of phosphate^{6,7} in the solutions of the samples, the experimental weight per cent error of the determination being ±0.50. Glass containers were found unsuitable for housing the systems because of interference by the dissolution of their ingredients. Potassium acid phthalate-sodium hydroxide and sodium diethyl-barbiturate-hydrochloric acid were used as buffer combinations of the medium of equilibration. The pH was measured with a line operated Beckman zeromatic pH meter before and after equilibration to ascertain its constancy. The buffer solutions were prepared in 0.165M solution of sodium chloride to maintain the activity coefficients of the dissolving species of apatites effectively constant. The apatite get colloiddally dispersed in their aqueous solutions due to their low solubilities and minute particle size. To test for efficient separation of the colloidal component, the suspensions of a series of saturated system of CaHA were filtered through a IG₄ sintered glass crucible (particle size retention 5-10 μ) and phosphorus contents of the filtrates compared with those of the corresponding filtrates obtained through a millipore filter (pore size ~10 mμ) fitted to a filter-holder attached to a hypodermic syringe. The phosphorus contents of the two filtrates were within limits of experimental error (±0.5 wt%). Extraneous ions dissolved due to momentary contact of the colloidal suspensions with the glass crucibles were found to be too low to affect the accuracy of subsequent analyses. Each system shaken mechanically at a regulated speed was set up by adding 0.2 of 200 mesh (B.S.S.) solute to 100 ml of the buffer solution prepared in CO₂-free water. The systems were housed in air-tight polyethylene containers to exclude the presence of carbon dioxide to avoid thereby any alteration in the pH of the dissolving medium and to prevent the formation of carbonate-apatite. The assembly was kept in a thermally insulated cabin maintained at 37±0.5°. The period of equilibration required for attainment of saturation was determined through

dissolution kinetics as described earlier⁸ and maintained at 24 hr for all the systems. A few ml each of chloroform and toluene were added to the stock solutions as well as to the systems to eliminate bacterial growth.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analyses and measured frequencies of the samples are listed in Table 1. The calcium hydroxylapatite and its solid solutions with barium and/or cadmium have hexagonal crystalline structure⁷ and are interesting examples of solid state of fairly simple molecules of tetrahedral symmetry where bands become allowed due to relaxation of the molecular symmetry⁹ selection rules due to the influence of site symmetry. The ideal symmetry of tribasic phosphate ion in the free or undistorted state is tetrahedral—a member of Td point group. In this ideal symmetry condition only a few absorption bands corresponding to ν₄ (570 cm⁻¹) and ν₃ (1075 cm⁻¹) of PO₄³⁻ and ν_s (3450 cm⁻¹) of OH⁻ were clearly observed. From the spectra of the samples (Table 1) it could be seen that the ν₃ and ν₄ frequencies corresponding to PO₄³⁻ ion and ν_s corresponding to OH⁻ ion are shifted to lower frequencies and the shape of the peaks was being affected by the introduction of Ba²⁺ and/or Cd²⁺ ion into the samples. The shift of the ν₃ and ν₄ of PO₄³⁻ vibrations to lower frequencies may be due to the effect of binding energy and atomic mass. The lowering of ν_s of OH⁻ indicates the presence of (hydrogen bonded) hydroxyl group in the apatite¹⁰. This hydroxyl group in hydroxylapatite lie in the inter-nuclear axis coincident with six fold screw axis. In Barnes expression¹¹ which gives a $\nu = \frac{1}{2\pi c} \sqrt{\frac{k}{\mu}}$ relationship between frequency, atomic mass and force constant, the vibrational frequencies are dependent on the reduced mass μ of the participating atoms and restoring force K between atoms. All other terms remaining constant K generally increases when the equilibrium distance between the positive and negative atoms of the molecule is decreased. This equilibrium

Fig. 1. Electron microscopic patterns of a representative set of samples of mixed (Ca+Ba+Cd) hydroxylapatite.

Fig. 2A

distance depends on the ionic radii of the participating atoms in the molecule. Substitution of Ca^{2+} with a nucleus like Ba^{2+} and/or Cd^{2+} gives rise to a stronger coordination of the PO_4^{3-} group to the Ba^{2+} and/or Cd^{2+} ion through oxygen. This in turn weakens the P-O bond, lowering K (increasing P-O bond length) and the frequency is lowered.

The homogeneity and crystallinity of the samples were confirmed by the values of their lattice parameters. The lattice parameter showed unit cell dilation consequent upon the introduction of Ba^{2+} (1.35 Å) ion and Cd^{2+} (0.97 Å) in place of 2 Ca^{2+} (0.99 Å) in the solid solutions of hydroxylapatites. The increase in the crystal dimension could also be observed in their electron-microscopic patterns of a representative set of the samples as given in Fig. 1.

The dependence of solubility of CaHA, BaHA, CdHA and their solid solutions on the pH of the dissolving medium are shown in Fig. 2. The solubility of each of the samples decreased with an increase in pH. The samples being salts of a weak acid undergo hydrolysis in aqueous media. The dissolved phosphate ions function as proton-acceptors accounting thereby for the observed pH dependence of the solubilities.

Fig. 2B. Dependence of solubilities of calcium, barium and cadmium hydroxylapatite and their mixed solid solutions on the pH of the dissolving medium.

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